

PIRLS - INTERNATIONAL READING LITERACY ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

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Annotation: The article is about the PIRLS International Literacy Assessment Program, which covers the countries and countries participating in the PIRLS International Assessment Program in 2021, including primary and secondary school students. goals in winter assessment, information on reading literacy levels are recorded.

Keywords: PIRLS, international research, primary education system

The PIRLS international study provides an international comparison of data on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students, which can serve as a public policy in the field of education in improving reading and teaching. is a major international evaluation program that provides analytics.

The PIRLS international assessment program in 2021 was attended by 4th graders from about 70 countries for the first time. The survey was conducted in 2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, and 2021 is the fifth period of the survey. Held every five years, the PIRLS program assesses 4th graders' reading comprehension skills internationally.

At present, according to the PIRLS definition, reading literacy is the ability to understand and use written language forms that are required and valued by society, as well as the ability to generate meaning from texts in various forms. show understanding

focuses on how to apply the information learned from doing to new projects and situations.

The student is an active participant in the process, creating meaning, observing the text, and consciously choosing effective reading strategies. Each type of text helps the reader to interpret the text using the usual forms and rules. Any text can take

many forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents, and newspapers, as well as digital written forms.

PIRLS focuses on two broad goals in assessing elementary students' classroom and extracurricular learning: "gaining artistic experience" and "obtaining and using information." Each of these goals, in turn, combines four broad processes of understanding. These are:

focus and find clear information;

draw direct conclusions;

evaluate and critique content and text elements;

interpreting and harmonizing ideas and information.

The complexity of the texts in the study ranged from an average of 500 to 800 words, 400–500 words for countries with low levels of student literacy, and about 1,000 words in the PIRLS. The content of the text is suitable for students aged 9-10 years, deviates from topics that are very specific to some cultures, as well as interesting and less familiar to the reader.

The PIRLS survey describes reading literacy levels as follows:

Highest level (625 points and above) - Students are able to master the text as a whole and at the same time understand its individual parts in relation to each other. Can rely on text to explain an author's idea.

Advanced (550 points) - Students understand important messages in the text, draw conclusions based on the text, evaluate both the content and the form of the text, and pay attention to some of its linguistic features.

Intermediate (475 points) - Students are able to find information in the text, use some features of the text form and language, and draw conclusions based on the text.

Low Level (400 points) - Students will be able to identify a message in a text that is clear and easy to restrict.

How well do Uzbek primary school graduates study compared to their peers in other countries? What is the reading literacy of Uzbek students? Is reading a hobby for 4th

graders? How does the family contribute to literacy? How is the process of teaching reading organized in our country today? Is the process of teaching reading in Uzbekistan unique from other countries, and if so, what is it? Are the methods used by our primary school teachers different from those used by teachers in other countries? basic issues such as The study also conducts questionnaires to study and analyze the factors that affect the quality of education.

In particular, information about the participant through the student survey, educational resources in the family, attitude to school, teacher, subject, relationship between students, self-knowledge on academic subjects assessment, information on extracurricular activities is collected.

The participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the PIRLS study will not only improve the quality of education, strengthen the country's image at the international level, but also bring students' knowledge to the level of international requirements.

References:

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